

EFFECT OF FOLIAR APPLICATION OF SALICYLIC ACID TO MITIGATE SALT STRESS IN WHEAT (*TRITICUM AESTIVUM* L.)

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Abstract

Salt stress is one of the most important abiotic factors that restricts plant growth and seed germination. Salicylic acid is a plant growth regulator that linked to defense responses to several stressors, including salt. The current study conducted to enhance the growth and yield of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) under salinity stress by foliar application of salicylic acid. Therefore, the goal of this study is to determine how salicylic acid influences the components of wheat yield under salt stress. For this purpose an experiment was conduct in the autumn season, 2021 at the Agronomic Research Area, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad. The experiment was performed with three replicates. In this study, there were two factors. Factor (A) various salt concentrations (0, 5 and 10 dsm⁻¹) was added to the soil. Salicylic acid values of (0, 75, 150 and 225 mgL⁻¹) was factor B. After seven days of salt treatment, a foliar spray of SA was applied. At the time of harvesting yield parameters, water use efficiency, grain protein and grain carbohydrates contents was determined. Best performance was seemed where less salt and more salicylic acid was used as in treatment of T₄ which is at par with T₃. Likewise minimum results gained from T₉. The collected data was analyze using standard statistical techniques. The least significant difference test (LSD) was performed to compare the differences between the treatments at a 5% probability level.

Keywords: Wheat, Salicylic Acid, Salinity Stress, Foliar Application.

INTRODUCTION

Wheat provides the human diet with important minerals, vitamins, amino acids, and phytochemicals as well as dietary fiber components, whole grain products are especially rich in these nutrients. Nevertheless, a variety of unfavorable reactions in people, like as

intolerances (particularly celiac disease) and allergies (both dietary and respiratory), are also linked to wheat products (Sherwy, 2009). Due to the presence of significant bioactive substances like vitamin E, carotenoids, and unsaturated fatty acids, wheat oil can be employed as an ingredient in food, medicinal, or cosmetic preparations (Durante *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, Energy (21 percent) and protein are primarily sourced from wheat. This is how 4.5 billion people around the planet will survive (Siddiq and Vemireddy, 2021). According to predictions, up to 2% annual production has increased and would be necessary until 2050 to fulfill the demands of growing population (Braun *et al.*, 2010).

Wheat is a crucial dietary component that has a positive nutritional influence on life quality. It is able to provide the greatest yield feasible while tolerating a variety of environmental situations. Wheat flour (*Triticum aestivum* L.), the product of 2 stages of hybridization, is an allohexaploid species (Salamini *et al.*, 2002). After cultivated wheat populations spread over Europe and Asia, they made local adaptations and became recognized as landraces. First arriving in Latin America, then moving on to Northern America and Australia, wheat bread was first present to the New Lands in the sixteenth century (Bonjean and Angus, 2001). Last but not least, during the Second World War, the introduction of dwarf genes into wheat and other crops during the Green Revolution caused significant changes in the global gene pool (Baenziger *et al.*, 2006). Greece received wheat in the year 8000 BC. Wheat also reached the Balkans, Italy, France, and Spain in the year 7000 BC. The United Kingdom and Scandinavia received wheat in the year 5000 BP (Bonjean *et al.*, 2001).

Cronin *et al.* (2021) observed that there are well-established associations between cereal eating and a decreased risk of developing cancer, type 2 diabetes, and cardio-vascular disease. Wheat is an exceptionally major kind of carbohydrate, with bread by itself constituting 20% of regular consumption in the UK (especially colo-rectal cancer). Punjab, Pakistan's largest province, accounts for 75% of the country's total agricultural output, placing Pakistan seventh in the world (Ahmad *et al.*, 2021). The industrialized use of salt water is increasing of concern due to the world's urban, industrialized, and agricultural sectors' rivalry and the rapidly growing need for water. By rising the consumption of Na⁺ ions and reducing the Na⁺/K⁺ ratio into plant roots on account of the negative osmotic pressure, salinity stress can lead to salt tolerance and oxidative damage. By increasing the intake of Na⁺ ions and decreasing the Na⁺/K⁺ ratio, plant roots are subjected to salt stress, oxidative stress, and negative osmotic potential (Arif *et al.*, 2020).

The most prevalent ions that produce a variety of physiological issues and negative impacts in plants are Na⁺ and Cl⁻. But Na⁺ is the most crucial ion because it prevents potassium (K⁺) uptake and interferes with stomatal regulation that results in water loss, meanwhile the Cl⁻ ion inhibits the formation of chlorophyll and produces in poisonous chlorotic consequences. Cl⁻, therefore, poses a greater risk than Na⁺ (Tavakkoli *et al.*, 2011). The Mehler process, which includes reduction of univalent oxygen at photosystem I, or direct transfer of the excited state from chlorophyll to form singlet oxygen are two

ways that reactive oxygen species can be generated in the chloroplast (Foyer *et al.*, 1994). H_2O_2 , an active oxygen species, is detoxified by these enzymes into water. If the plant response and newly introduced biological or environmental improvements to stress tolerance are to be understood, it is imperative to elucidate the processes through which plants detect and transmit these stresses (Borsani *et al.*, 2001).

Plant hormones are chemical substances, either synthetic or naturally occurring, that are utilized to alter the growth or yield of plants. PGR artificial substances that are used to limit plant growth without impacting the plants' production (Leolato *et al.*, 2017; Nazeer *et al.*, 2020). It is a white, odourless powder with the chemical formula $C_7H_6O_3$, and it functions in plants to control enzymes and plant development hormones. Salicylic acid may have an effects on growth, stomatal regulation, plant water relations, and photosynthesis (Ghassemi and Farhadi, 2021). It was believed that SA would defend cells and eliminate reactive oxygen species (ROS).

When exposed to salt stress, seedlings respond by altering the function of scavenger enzymes such CAT, SOD, polyphenol oxidase (PPO), and POX. SA enhances salt tolerance, lessens the antioxidative enzymes activation throughout germination, and lessens consequences of salt stress. The capacity of SA to provide a protective impact on plants beneath the influence in terms of stressors of various abiotic nature has also attracted a lot of attention recently. As a result, evidence that the SA increased the susceptibility of wheat seedlings to salt has been gathered water obstacle (Bezrukova, 2001), of Higher as well as lower temperatures can harm plants like those of the tomato and bean (Senaratna *et al.*, 2000), and toxic metals can harm wheat plants (Mishra and Choudhuri, 1999). SA may be linked to improved photosynthesis and decreased transpiration rate, which jointly improved drought-tolerant water usage efficiency. Furthermore, the findings suggest that SA might be used in the future as a possible growth regulator to enhance plant development and production in situations where soil water supply is constrained (Singh and Usha, 2003).

Contradictory effects of SA have been observed, including opposite trends in stress tolerance. This investigation's goal is to determine how foliar-applied SA impacts wheat seedlings' susceptibility to salt, H_2O_2 generation, and antioxidant enzyme activity (Sawada *et al.*, 2008). Young wheat seedlings' roots' SOD and peroxidase (POX) activities were decreased as an outcome of SA's reduction of the level of active oxygen species (Shakirova *et al.*, 2003).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was carried out under environmental condition of Faisalabad at Agronomic Research Area, Department of Agronomy, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad. Seeds of Akbar 19 variety in different concentration of saline soil was sown. Climatic data of experimental site showed in (Figure 1). Soil property of experimental site is discussed in (Table 1).

Table 1: Physico-chemical Composition of Soil

Electrical conductivity (dSm ⁻¹)	0.80
PH	7.70
Organic matter (%)	0.69
Available-P (ppm)	20.00
Available-K (ppm)	80.00
Saturation (%)	38.00
Texture	Loam
Remarks	Normal soil

The trail was conducted during the first week of November. The study was done under Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with factorial arrangement with three times replications. Factor A comprises of foliar spray of Salicylic acid with different concentration (Control, 75, 150 and 225 mg/L⁻¹) which is represented by (T) and Factor B consist on various concentration of salt stress (0, 5 and 10 dsm⁻¹) which is represented by (S). The field well prepared according to recommendation and crop were sown by using drill. To meet the nutrient requirement of crop, the N:P:K were provided with in the ratio of 120:80:60 kg Acre⁻¹ respectively. To meet the water requirement the field were irrigated frequently. The crop was harvested manually and sun dried for 3-5 days after harvesting. The data of different variables was recorded by following standard procedureds. ANOVA technique will be utilized to analyze the collected data. For comparing the difference between the treatments at a 5% level of significance, the least significant difference test (LSD) of 5 % probability will be used (Steel *et al.*, 1997).

Figure 1: Climatic Data of Experimental Site

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plant Height (cm)

Plant height is one of the most crucial growth stage variables. Morphological traits of plants identified that the growth of a plant depends on plant height that is characterized by various parameters, for example, stem elongation, a genetic feature of cultivars, environment characters, nutrition, uptake, and vigor of seed. Cultivars having more plant height are susceptible to lodging with respect to new varieties, declining the yield of the crop because due to lodging, flag leaf is unable to utilize maximum sunlight and minimum contributions towards grain filling.

Data showed that plant height highly effected by the application of SA (Salicylic Acid) under different salt concentrations figure 2. The highest plant height recorded in T₄ followed by S₁T₃ whereas the minimal plant height was recorded from T₉. Our findings closely match those that have been reported by (idrees *et al.*, 2011) as only the greatest concentrations of foliar spray salicylic acid (400 ppm), compared to the treatment under control (water spray), significantly increased plant height by about 11%. The outcome display that spraying wheat leaves with salicylic acid, the damaging effects of salinity stress on its development could be reduced. Research has shown that SA can improve abiotic stress plant growth in a number of areas, including nutrient uptake, water relations, stomatal regulation, photosynthesis, and growth (Arfan *et al.*, 2007). Young wheat seedlings grew more quickly when SA was added. When components of yield structure were examined in field studies, same effect was also observed (Shakirova *et al.*, 2003).

Figure 2: Effect of foliar application of salicylic acid to mitigate salt stress for plant height of wheat

Total Number of Tillers (m⁻²)

Data regarding to this parameter demonstrated that the maximum total number of tillers observed in treatment T₄ at par with T₃ whereas minimum was seemed in treatment T₉ as shown in figure 3. Overall findings demonstrate that salicylic acid at high doses together reduce salinity. Plant growth may be influenced by salicylic acid application (Kazeem *et al.*, 2019).

Number of Productive Tillers (m⁻²)

Interactive effect of number of productive tillers seemed as maximum in T₄ followed by T₃. Minimum values of this parameter depicted in T₉ (figure 3). Gutierrez Coronado *et al.* (1998) noted a notable effect of SA on wheat increases in no. of productive tillers. According to Khodary (2004), SA boosted the productive tillers in wheat plants that were under salt stress.

Figure 3: Effect of foliar application of salicylic acid to mitigate salt stress for total number of tillers and productive tillers of wheat

Spike length (cm)

Statically maximum spike length was observed in T₄, which was statically at part with T₃, where statistically minimum spike length was found in T₉. The highest spike weights per plants were produced by treating wheat plants with 225mg L⁻¹ salicylic acid (figure 4). A little concentration of salicylic acid can help plants tolerate unfavorable situation, because taking a much of salicylic acid can raise your oxidative stress stages and diminish stress tolerance (Dong *et al.*, 2015). The physiological and biochemical activities of plants are known to be impacted by SA and other salicylates, which may be crucial in controlling the growth and productivity of plants. (Hayat *et al.*, 2010).

Number of grains per spike

The quantity of grains per spike is a significant yield-contributing factor in the production of wheat yield. Spikes that are sterile having no grain ultimately decline the production of wheat and decline the harvest index of crops. The genetic make-up of cultivars and agronomic techniques both influence the number of grains per panicle i.e. having appropriate management of weeds, adequate supply of nutrients, and better water use efficiency. Figure 4 showed that statically maximum number of grains per spike was observed in T₄, which was statically at part with T₃, where statistically minimum spike length was found in T₉. When in contrast to the control plant, the salinity treatment's drop dry weight in the grains (Kazem *et al.*, 2019).

Number of spikelets per spike

Interactive effect of number of spikelets per spike seemed as maximum in T₄ followed by T₃. Minimum values of this parameter depicted in T₉ figure 4. These outcomes were comparable to those of research by El-Tayeb (2005) reported that the stressed wheat seedlings received an increase in number of spikelets per spike.

Figure 4: Effect of foliar application of salicylic acid to mitigate salt stress for spike length, number of spikelets per spike and number of grains per spike of wheat

Thousand Grain Weight

Data (figure 5) showed that 1000-grain weight highly effected by the application of SA (Salicylic Acid) under different salt concentrations. The highest weight of a thousand

grains was noted in T₄ followed by T₃ while minimum 1000 grain weight was recorded from T₉. These outcomes are comparable to those found by and Afzal *et al.*, (2005), who discovered that salt stress in wheat reduced dry weight or 1000 grain weight.

Grain Yield (t ha⁻¹)

The primary factors that considerably increase wheat's grain output are the maximum 1000 grain weight, the number of grains per spike, the length of the panicle, and the number of branches per panicle. (Jabran *et al.*, 2015). According to scientists, differences in rice grain production due to variations in genetic features and environmental circumstances, as well as agronomic and cultural techniques, greatly influence rice grain output.

Statically maximum grain yield was observed in T₄, which was statically at par with T₃, where statistically minimum grain yield was found in T₉. The grain yield of wheat reduced with increasing the salinity level (figure 5). Akher *et al.* (2018) stated that a high salinity could cause a 37% loss in grain yield per plant by shortening the spikes and diminishing the grain.

Biological Yield (t ha⁻¹)

The sum of grain yield and straw yield is called biological yield. Biological yield of rice is foremost important yield contributing trait in wheat production. Data regarding to this parameter demonstrated that the maximum biological yield observed in treatment T₄ at par with T₃ whereas minimum was seemed in treatment T₉ (figure 5). SA and other salicylates are known to influence a range of physiological and biochemical processes in plants, and it's possible that these effects will be crucial in controlling the plants' growth and yield (Hayat *et al.*, 2010).

Harvest Index (%)

A determinant of crop productivity is the harvest index (HI). Owing to its crucial part in crop plants' expression of grain output, the harvest index is significant. Harvest index % of wheat is foremost important yield contributing trait in wheat production. Maximum grain weight, number of grain per spike, spike length and number of branches per panicle are main parameters that significantly enhanced the yield of harvest index % rice (Jabran *et al.*, 2015).

Scientist reported that harvest index % of wheat majorly depends on agronomic and culture practices and the variation in harvest index % is due to variation in genetic traits and environmental condition. Data (figure 5) showed that harvest index highly effected by the application of SA (Salicylic Acid) under different salt concentrations. The maximum harvest index was observed in T₄ followed by T₃ while minimum was recorded from T₉. A little concentration of salicylic acid can help plants tolerate unfavorable situation, because taking a much of salicylic acid can raise your oxidative stress stages and diminish stress tolerance (Dong *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 5: Effect of foliar application of salicylic acid to mitigate salt stress for 1000 grain weight, harvest index, grain yield and biological yield of wheat

Water Use Efficiency (%)

Data showed (figure 6) that water use efficiency highly effected by the application of SA (Salicylic Acid) under different salt concentrations. The maximum water use efficiency was observed in T₄ followed by T₃ while minimum was recorded from T₉.

Figure 6: Effect of foliar application of salicylic acid to mitigate salt stress for water use efficiency of wheat

Grain Protein Contents (%)

Data (figure 7) regarding to this parameter demonstrated that the maximum grain protein content observed in treatment T₄ at par with T₃ whereas minimum was seemed in treatment T₉. In treatments, SA enhanced radicle and plumule length and weight. Intense stress administration without SA pre-treatment and with lowest grain weight were likewise associated with the lowest grain protein contents. (Esfandiar *et al.*, 2012).

Grain Carbohydrates (%)

Data (figure 7) regarding to this parameter demonstrated that the maximum grain carbohydrates observed in treatment T₄ at par with T₃ whereas minimum was seemed in treatment T₉. For grain carbohydrates, obvious responses were seen in saline conditions (Pirasteh *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 7: Effect of foliar application of salicylic acid to mitigate salt stress for grain protein contents and grain carbohydrate contents of wheat

Correlation

The figure 8 showed that total number of tillers had highly significant correlation with plant height, number of productive tiller had highly positive plus significant correlation with plant the height and total number of tillers, spike length had also highly significant and highly positive correlation with plant height, total number of tillers and number of productive tillers, number of grain per spike had highly positive and highly significant correlation with plant height, total number of tillers, number of productive tillers and spike length.

Grain yield had highly significant and highly positive correlation with plant height, total number of tillers, number of productive tillers, spike length, number of grain per spike, number of spikelet's per spike and 1000 grain weight. Biological yield had positive and non-significant correlation with plant height, total number of tillers, number of productive tillers, spike length and 1000 grain weight.

Water use efficiency, grain protein contents and grain carbohydrate contents had positive correlation and highly significant correlation with plant height, total number of tillers, number of productive tillers, spike length, number of grain per spike, number of spikelet's per spike, 1000 grain weight, grain yield, biological yield and harvest index.

* $p \leq 0.05$ ** $p \leq 0.01$

Figure 8: Correlation assessment among studied traits i.e. plant height (PH), Total Number of Tillers (TNT), Number of Productive Tillers (NPT), Spike Length (SL), Number of Grains Per Spike (NGPS), Number of Spikelets Per Spike (NSPS), 1000 Grain Weight (1000 GW), Grain Yield (GY), Biological Yield (BY), Harvest Index (HI), Water Use Efficiency (WUE), Grain Protein Contents (GPC) and Grain Carbohydrate Contents (GC)

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that with the application of salicylic acid have positive effect on agronomic trait. The lowest values for agronomic trait were obtained from T₉ from where we have higher concentration 10dS⁻¹ of salinity stress.

Highest agronomic trait was obtained from T₄ followed by T₃. SA could be used as a potential growth regulator to improve wheat growth under salinity conditions.

Author Contributions

All authors have equally contributed to conduct this trial.

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